

10.5281/zenodo.13383838

Socio-Psychological Variables And Secondary School Adolescents Adjustments In Bayelsa State

***Brown, G. Mother, Prof. I. R Ernest-Ehibudu & Prof. C. J. Ugwu**

**Department of Educational Psychology Guidance & Counselling
Faculty of Education,
University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Nigeria
*E-mail: vivianbrownie58@gmail.com**

ABSTRACT

This study focused on socio-psychological variables and secondary school adolescent's adjustments in Bayelsa State. Correlational research design was adopted in the study. The population of the study consisted of 24,769 SS2 students in the 192 public secondary schools in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The sample size for the study was 560 SS2 drawn using the multi-stage sampling technique. Two instruments were used for the study. They include the Socio-Psychological Variables Questionnaire (SPQ) as well as the Adolescents School Adjustment Questionnaire (ASAQ). Face validity of the instruments was established by experts in Measurement and Evaluation. The reliability was determined using Cronbach Alpha method with indices of 0.81 and 0.71 respectively. PPMC was used to analyze the data collected in the process. Result of the findings showed that family conflict ($p=0.033<0.05$) and self-esteem ($p=0.024<0.05$) have significant relationship with school adjustment. On the contrary, family values ($p=0.41>0.05$) was insignificantly related with school adjustment of adolescents. Based on this, it was recommended among others that parent should mind the type of interaction between their partners in the presence of the children since this can cause either positive or negative adjustments in the life of the children.

Keywords: Family Conflict, Family Values, Self-Esteem, Adolescent, Adjustment.

INTRODUCTION

The stage of adolescence is a phase of change, maturity, development, discovery of one's identity, appreciating and realizing of one's individuality and of learning to maintain that individuality while interfacing with surrounding culture (Brown, 2009). Agbakwuru and Ekechukwu cited in Brown (2009) noted that that it is the ultimate phase of development in the path towards maturity. Adolescence is a phase in human life which begins biologically with physiological changes of the pubis and ends psychologically with the eventual organization of sexuality as opined by Agbakwuru and Ekechukwu (2009). This is a period of transition marked by the inception of puberty and eventual termination of physical growth; cognitive development for abstract and multidimensional thinking, emotional maturation and social initiation into adult roles (Rathus, as cited in Brown 2009). At this transitional period characterized by biological, cognitive, emotional and social changes, when the adolescents evolve into adulthood, they want to appreciate and consummate their new roles, ideas and feelings. This exploration of self and new found independence can bring about feelings of anxiety and uncertainty on how to fit into the dynamics and confusing world around them and be accepted by society. Adolescence encompasses the period ranging from 10 to 21 years (Igbo in Onwuasoanya,

2008). This is a period when young children are developing into adulthood, extending from puberty to independence. It has three stages namely; early adolescence from 10 to 14 years, middle adolescence from 15 to 17 years and late adolescence from 17 to 21 years (Onwuasoanya, 2008). It is a period of the life cycle between childhood and adulthood with some unique characteristics connected with development and marked by dramatic challenges that requires adjustment to changes in self, in the family and peer group (Santrock, 2008).

In terms of physical changes, the adolescent experiences physical growth, sexual maturation, intense emotional, social, cognitive and personal development. This developmental period is described as a time of storm and stress; conflict and crisis of adjustment and a stage of feelings of rejection and failure as they go through the physical, emotional and social developmental stages and the search for self, (Hahn and Payn, 2011). The categories of individuals described above are people found to be in their late primary schools to tertiary schools for those who are going to school. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines adolescents as those people between 10 and 19 years of age. The great majority of adolescents are, included in the age-based definition of “child”, adopted by the Convention on the Rights of The Child. However, for this research, the focus is on those within the later stage of early adolescence from 10 to 14 years and middle adolescence from 15 to 17 years usually in senior secondary schools.

As noted by the researcher, there are so many challenges facing the adolescent child in the society today. People have observed that while some of these problems may arise from the individual families, some are just peculiar to the individuals themselves. It is believed that the transitional period between teen and adulthood has a great challenge. This period which is recognized as the “Adolescence” period is often greeted with various challenges with respect to some individuals. Some of these challenges range from peer intimidation, social acceptance, problem of independence etc. Ekeremo (2008) re-echoed this period is a period of stress, storm, indecision, mistakes and confusion.

Adjustment is a natural phenomenon that every individual must experience one way or the other. Students experience change in their educational journey, from one class of ascending to one level of education to the other. In these scholarly processes, they are faced with a new environment or a new operation of the school system which comes with its challenges, leaving them with a choice. Being accustomed to a particular environment is a soothing and comfortable feeling that allows one to engage freely, thereby contributing and benefitting from that environment. Adjustment is simply making room for new changes. Shaver (2018) stated that adjustment is a behaviour that keeps people and other creatures in balance between their varied requirements and the constraints of their environments. In essence, individuals must strive to find a balance in whatever changing situations they find themselves. It therefore requires one to become acclimatized to any new environment or situation they find themselves.

Adjustment can be internal or an external phenomenon. Internal adjustment refers to the psychological needs; such as love, acceptance, security, etc, that occurs within an individuals’ environment. External adjustment refers to the change or adaptation that occurs around the environment an individual. These includes; changing a job, moving to a new location, changing a school etc. (Sharma, 2016). All of these play a significant role in secondary school students' adjustment. Definitely, the learning process or the school structure could be upgraded or downgraded depending on circumstances; however, it is the responsibility of students to find a way to embrace the change by way of finding a balance. However, it is what one is exposed to that forms the basis of their actions. Okpara and Onyekuru (2013) believe that the school transition of the learners are hinged on the compatibility of their desires, abilities, and the requirement within learning setting. Parents are also known as the pillars on which children can anchor, they form the foundation of the child as they are the ones the child learn from and relate with more. Therefore, Parental upbringing cannot be overlooked when it comes to adjustment, studies have emphasized on how parents affect their children's adjustment.

School is one of the important pillars on which the child’s personality is formed. It is the place where children have contacts with peers, form friendship and participate in social groups with other children. Through adolescence, peers become increasingly important in their lives. Their interaction become

more complex with age. At this stage, social support from friends can assist the children to adjust well in school and to be able to handle situations related to school environment. However, if the individual is unable to adjust well, he or she may become maladjusted due to stress and so underachieve. Stress is very common among adolescent boys and girls of school stage. Stress is partly created by parental pressure when they expect their adolescents to perform and stand out among their peer groups, when they cannot rise up to such expectations, they suffer frustration, aggression, undesirable complexes and depression. These psychological situations are attributable to the adolescents' inability to adjust to the demands of his immediate environment (the school).

It is worth noting that, the challenges such adolescents must likely face is that of school adjustment. School adjustment is the ability of students to relate freely and easily with others in the school in relation to their unique personalities (Darner, 2009). It is the ability of individuals to adapt to any type of behavioural dispositions displayed by others without carrying negative feelings. In essence, in school, students will always exhibit who they are. Demirtas and Ergene (2019) observed that the freedom given to a child from home tend to find expression through the child's adjustment. However, his/her ability to accept or comply with school rules or relate with other students may be influence by their home training. Therefore, the ability of adolescents to relate properly while in school with friends and school authorities irrespective of the situation they find themselves necessitates the present study.

The school is an integral part of education and as such, it cannot be overlooked considering the fast-rising evolution of technology and new knowledge, there is a great need for stability and focus in order to gain proper cognitive growth. This is a process every student will experience, in other words, there will never be a time when a child will remain in one class forever. Growth will always require a student to move from one level of education to the other, one of such ascending levels of growth has the secondary at one level which is a basic prerequisite for a university education. Again, with the passing of time and new expectations of the society based on development, the school will need to upgrade their policies and systems as there is every likelihood to upgrade to meet the standards and expectations of the society which impacts on the educational system.

The school therefore is the predicate on which adjustment hangs on. Lakhani, Jain and Chandel, (2017) viewed school adjustment as the acts of becoming accustomed of the rigors accompanying being a student and to the multiple characteristics of the educational setting. It is the process where a student's behaviour is streamlined to suit the norms of the school setting (Agbakwuru, 2009). This has to do with subjecting one's emotions, thoughts and attitudes to the dictates or expectations of a school which is a gradual process as it is not automatic. Furthermore, in the words of Lakhani, Jain, and Chandel (2017), learners go to school at different levels of development, under different environmental influences, with different social attitudes and behaviour. They also have different cultures and ethnic orientations. How these individuals progress over time with their diverse psychosocial characteristics is an important area of educational research. One of such psychosocial traits is the ability of an individual to adjust effectively into a new environment, especially as it concerns transition from one school level to another. However, it is also worth noting that the level or extent of adjustment may be influenced by a number of things. Again, it could be that the prevalent of societal issues that has posed a serious threat to school adjustment of the adolescents all over the world, in Nigeria and even in Bayelsa State, the condition of the family in terms of the level of conflict, values as well as the attachment patterns prevalent in the family may play certain roles in determining the social adjustment of children.

According to Kemjika and Obikoya (2007) conflict refers to some form of friction, disagreement, or discord arising within a group when the beliefs or actions of one or more members of the group are either resisted or unacceptable to one or more members of another group. Conflict can arise between members of the same group, known as intra-group conflict, or it can occur between members of two or more groups, and involve violence, interpersonal discord, and psychological tension, known as intergroup conflict. Family conflict according to Malek (2013) is any conflict that occurs within a family; between husbands and wives, parents and children, between siblings, or with extended families (grandparents, aunts, uncles, etc.). Family conflict is different from other types of conflict for several

reasons. First, family members are already highly emotionally attached. These emotions can quickly intensify conflict. Secondly, family members are involved in long-term relationships and often are required to interact with one another daily. Finally, families are often insular, obeying their own rules and resisting outside interference. These characteristics can lead to long, tangled, painful conflicts. At one extreme, family conflict can lead to things like divorce or domestic violence. At the other, families try to repress conflict, avoiding problems and detaching from each other. Furthermore, examples of family conflicts are: fighting between husbands and wives, sibling rivalry and parent-child power struggles, quarrelling among family members, spouse nagging, disagreement etc. Many families face difficult struggles that are often quite volatile and troubling.

Iruloh, Ernest-Ehibudu, and Echebe (2009) stated that conflict refers to any block that a client is experiencing in his development. Such conflict areas include; conflict with people, family, self, lack of knowledge and skill requisite to personal achievement. Conflict in this context, is one of the most studied and discussed subjects in the area of family communication. Family conflict as described by Malak (2013) is any conflict that occurs within a family; between husbands and wives, parents and children, between siblings, or with extended families (grandparents, aunts, uncles, etc). On a personal note, the researcher has experienced situations where a father and mother of a student come to visit the student separately, if by chance both parents show up together, there will be disagreement, chaos, to the extent the school's management has to come in and reschedule their visit to the student. Families in general and parents in particular, have often been deemed to be the most important support system available to the child. The strongest factor in molding a child's personality or behaviour is his/her relationship with his/her parents. However, no matter how loving a family is, all families go through conflict.

Demirtaş-Zorbaz and Ergene (2019) studied school adjustment of first-grade primary school students: Effects of family involvement, externalizing behavior, teacher and peer relations their result showed that family involvement has no statistically significant direct influence on first-grade students' school adjustment. In addition, externalizing behaviors affect school adjustment through the mediating role of teacher-student relationship and peer relations. Also, the total effect of the externalizing behavior variable on school adjustment is -0.55 . The student-teacher relationship ($B = 0.53$) and peer relationship ($B = 0.48$) variables have also had an effect on school adjustment. Kader and Roman (2018) also studied the effects of family conflict on the psychological needs and externalizing behaviour of preadolescents. Their findings indicated a significant positive relationship between family conflict, psychological needs and the externalizing behaviour of preadolescents. Similarly, Kemjika and Obikoya (2017) studied relationship between family conflict, values and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in rivers state. The results of the study showed that there is a positive relationship between family conflict, values and school adjustment which are all statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance.

The values which each family has may play a role in the extent of school adjustments of individuals. In this dispensation of modernization, moral codes, and principles, have been neglected in the name of civilization. Some families even leave their adolescents in the hands of care-givers and no longer pay as much attention to their adolescents as required. Family values are traditional or cultural values (that is, values passed on from generation to generation within families) that pertain to the family's structure, function, roles, beliefs, attitudes, and ideals (Wikipedia (2016), In the social sciences, sociologists may use the term "traditional family" in order to refer specifically to the child-rearing environment that sociologists formerly called the norm.

Family value is defined as the moral and ethical principles traditionally upheld and transmitted within a family, such as honesty, loyalty, hard work, and faith. Family values are values especially of a traditional or conservative kind which are held to promote the sound functioning of the family and to strengthen the fabric of society. Webster dictionary (2014). In addition, Oxford dictionaries.com (2014) define family values as values held to be traditionally learned or reinforced within a family, such as those high moral standards and discipline. A close examination of the definitions and explanations given concerning family values reveals that family values are simply a set of rules and regulations of behaviour handed down by families to generations. These behavior codes create

structure in families and can define each member's role. They also help families cope with difficult challenges and determine right from wrong in complex situations. These shared principles can impact many areas of a family's life, including: Daily activities, disciplinary techniques for children, division of chores, education, finances, parenting styles, relationships, religion, rituals etc.

Each family has unique core values based on the priorities and needs of individual members. These principles often transmit inter-generationally, traveling from grandparent to parent to child. For example, children generally learn norms and personality traits from their parents. Researchers still don't fully understand this complex phenomenon, but studies suggest that culture, gender, and other factors may play a role in how family values travel between generations. Thus, the transmission of values by schools and families plays a very important role in adolescence stage of life. Georgas, (1999) stated that family values refer to attitudes towards roles, responsibilities and hierarchies in the family. These family values form a cultural notion through which the experiences of well-being are influenced. Among others, within the African context, great value is placed on marriage and the social protection it offers (Addai, et al. 2015 and Gyekey, 1997), making it necessary for couples to strive to continuously preserve marital harmony (Osei-Tutu et al., 2019). This could imply that individuals who endorse prevailing family values, given its relational nature, and cultural contextualization are more likely to have higher levels of well-being. Geel and Vedder (2011) studied the Role of Family Obligations and School Adjustment in Explaining the Immigrant Paradox. Family obligations and school adjustment were found positively related to adaptation outcomes in the national and the immigrant adolescent sample. The findings also suggest that in underprivileged environments, a strong sense of family obligations may help immigrants as well as national adolescents achieve a positive pattern of adaptation. Olaitan (2017) also studied the impact of family structure on the academic performance of secondary school students in Yewa Local Government Area of Ogun State, Nigeria. Results showed a significant difference in the academic performance of students from single parent families and those from two parent families. In other words, the academic performance of children from two parent families is better than those from single parent families. The implications of the findings were that parental separation should be avoided. Uwaifo (2012) examined the effect of family structure on the academic performance of University students in Nigeria. The results showed that significant differences existed between the academic performance of students from single-parent family and those from two-parent family structures. The results also indicated significant differences in academic performance of male and female students compared on two types of family structures. On the basis of these findings, it was recommended that school counsellors should be employed in all schools and that they should provide necessary assistance to students especially those from single-parent family to enable them overcome their emotional concerns. Similarly, Uwaifo (2008) examined the effects of family structure and parenthood on the academic performance of Nigerian university students. The results showed that significant differences existed between the academic performance of students from single-parent family and those from two-parent family structures. The results also indicated significant differences in academic performance of male and female students compared on two types of family structures. Ella, Odok and Ella (2015) studied the influence of family size and family type on academic performance of students in Government in Calabar Municipality, Cross River State, Nigeria. The result revealed a significant influence of family size and family type on academic performance of secondary school students in Government in Calabar Municipality, Cross River State, Nigeria.

Self-esteem has to do with a person's overall assessment of his/her personal worth. It is an individual's subjective evaluation of their own worth. It encompasses beliefs about oneself as well as emotional states such as triumph, despair, pride and shame. Psychologist usually regard self-esteem as an enduring personality characteristic though normal, short term variation also exist. It means having confidence on oneself, a satisfaction of what one is and the self-respect that confidence brings. Self-esteem has high and low; through thinking positively about oneself, one can develops his or her talents and abilities. Hence, people who feel good about themselves tend to be happy, healthy, successful and productive. They also tend to persist longer to difficult task, sleep better at night and have lesser

disease. On the other hand, low self-esteem makes people fearful and unrealistic about goals and risks. These further dents their self-images and leads to low performance (Obidigbo, 2011, Etel & Nwankwo 2019). Smith and Mackie (2007) stated that self-esteem is the positive or negative evaluation of self as in how one feels about it. It is an attractive psychological construct that predicts certain outcomes. Psychologist usually regard self-esteem as an enduring personality characteristic (trait, self-esteem), short-term variations (state self-esteem) also exist. From this premise, it could be that the self-esteem of the adolescents could play a greater part on the extent to which they adjust to school life. Suspiciously, it could be that adolescents will adjust positively if they have a good self-esteem and vice versa in terms of a poor or low self-esteem. Devi (2023) studied Self-Esteem of Secondary School Student in Relation of Educational Adjustment. Result depicted that moderate significant correlation was found between Government and Private School students. Yadav and Srivastava (2021) studied Self-esteem and adjustment among students. The result of this study showed that significant difference in self-esteem among hosteller and non-hosteller students. And significant difference was found in adjustment (emotional, social, and educational) among hosteller and non-hosteller students. The study revealed that significant relationship of self-esteem and adjustment among students. Pasha and Munaf (2013) investigated the relationship between the various dimensions of self-esteem and five domains of adjustment of traditional university freshmen (N=83) in the first semester of their Masters program. In all these, it is seen that the rate of family conflict which is ravaging through our society like wildfire is a pathetic case that calls for serious and prompt action from all sectors of the society. There is an increased rate of families who are violent and uninvolved in the lives of their adolescents, and this problem has eaten deep in families in the contemporary societies leads to family disharmony which in turn leads to separation, divorce and home desertion. This has also resulted into adolescent unhealthy attachment pattern to peers with alarming behavioural disorders, social conflict, and poor adjustment to school life. These children who do not get adequate attention from home becomes emotionally attached to their peers and look up to them for validation. Again, these children may become vulnerable to attacks from people who prey on neglected children as this will eventually produce children with low self-esteem, mental imbalance, low academic performance and poor adjustment to school life. Any transition that occurs in the life of a child, adolescent or adult can prove to be a time of anxiety, vulnerability, or even stress for that person, whether this transition is a normative or a non-normative one. The transition from one school level to another is a normative one yet quite significant process that every child and adolescent of school going age must go through.

Failure to address the problem of family conflict, family values and family attachment patterns in school adjustment of secondary school adolescents could result into more terrible psychological and physical consequences for the adolescents especially in Bayelsa State. These problems create a toxic school environment which makes it impossible for other students to learn better, and the consequential effect of this is also evident. Most of these students as a result, avoid school or at a point may even become dropouts. Hence, the study sorted to investigate socio-psychological variables and school adjustment of secondary school students.

Aim and Objectives

The aim of this study is to investigate socio-psychological variables and school adjustment of secondary school students in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study has the following objectives:

1. To find out the relationship between family conflict and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State.
2. To find out the relationship between family values and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State.
3. To examine the relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

In order to achieve the objectives of the study, the following research questions were postulated to guide the researcher in the study:

1. To what extent does family conflict relate with school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State?
2. What is the extent of relationship between family values and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State?
3. What is the extent of relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study and was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between family conflict and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State.
2. Family values have no significant relationship with school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State.
3. There is no significant relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the correlational research design. The population of the study consist of all SS2 students in the 192 public secondary schools in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. This comprises of 24,769 senior secondary school students in class 2 (SS2). (Source: Bayelsa State Senior Secondary Schools Board, 2021). The researcher chose this population because she believes they are the best respondents to give accurate response since they are in the adolescence development stage. The sample size for this study is 560 SS2 students which drawn using the multi-stage sampling technique. Three instruments were used for the study. They include the Socio-Psychological Variables Questionnaire (SPQ) as well as the Adolescents School Adjustment Questionnaire (ASAQ). Face validity of the instruments was established by experts in Measurement and Evaluation. The reliability was determined using Cronbach Alpha method with indices of 0.81 and 0.71 respectively. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and multiple regression were used to analyze the data collected in the process. Specifically, research questions 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7 and 8 were analyzed using PPMC. There corresponding hypotheses were analyzed using sig values associayed with the PPMC. On the other hand, resercah question 5, 9 and 10 were analyzed using multiple regression. Their corresponding hypotheses were analyzed using ANOVA associated with the regression analysis. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *To what extent does family conflict relate with school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State?*

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between family conflict and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State.

Table 1; Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis of relationship between family conflict and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State.

Variables	N	r	r²	Alpha	Sig	Result
Family conflict.	560	-0.357	0.127	0.05	0.033	Significant
School Adjustment	560					

The analysis in table 1 show that calculated r is -0.357. The r value shows that family conflict has a negative relationship with school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State meaning that as family conflict rises, there will be a reduction in school adjustment abilities of adolescents. The r² value is 0.127. This means that family values account for about 12.7% of variation

in school adjustment among adolescents. Calculated sig value is 0.033. Since the sig value (0.033<0.05) is less than the alpha of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected meaning that There is a significant relationship between family conflict and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State.

Research Question Two: *What is the extent of relationship between family values and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State?*

Hypothesis Two: Family values have no significant relationship with school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State.

Table 2; Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis of relationship between family values and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State.

Variables	N	r	r ²	Alpha	Sig	Result
Family values	560	0.035	0.001	0.05	0.414	Insignificant
School Adjustment	560					

The analysis in table 2 show that calculated r is 0.035. The r value shows that family values has a positive relationship with school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State. This means that if family value rises, there will be a corresponding rise in school adjustment abilities of adolescents. The r² value is 0.001. This means that family values account for about only 0.1% of variation in school adjustment among adolescents. Calculated sig value is 0.414. Since the sig value (0.414>0.05) is higher than the alpha of 0.05, the null hypothesis is retained meaning that there is no significant relationship between family values and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State.

Research Question Three: *What is the extent of relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State?*

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State.

Table 3; Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis of relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State.

Variables	N	r	r ²	Alpha	Sig	Result
Self-esteem	560	0.468	0.210	0.05	0.024	Significant
School Adjustment	560					

The analysis in table 3 show that calculated r is 0.468. The r value shows that self-esteem has a positive relationship with school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State. This means that if the value of self-esteem rises, there will be a corresponding rise in school adjustment abilities of adolescents. The r² value is 0.210. This means that self-esteem account for about 21% of total variation in school adjustment among adolescents. Calculated sig value is 0.024. Since the sig value (0.024<0.05) is less than the alpha of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected meaning that there is a significant relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State.

DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

From research findings one, it is revealed that there is a significant relationship between family conflict and school adjustment of secondary school adolescent in Bayelsa State. This finding means that the extent to which adolescent experience conflict in their family can affect their level of

adjustment in school. The implication of this is that adolescents who come from high conflict homes may find it difficult to adjust properly. It could be that those from families where the parent fight and quarrel every time may also adopt such pattern with other students or classmates in school as they may be involved in a lot of fighting which indicate lack of adjustment. In other words, adolescents from calm and peaceful home can easily adjust or get along with other students and teachers in school. The finding of the study may come because majority of the respondent are quite aware of the negative impact of family conflict on school adjustment of students. The findings of the study is not surprising to the researcher because as a counselor who have worked with adolescents, she has realize that those without proper adjustment usually have history of a dysfunctional family. Hence, the findings of the study are expected by the researcher. This finding is in line with that reported earlier by Demitas-Zoberg and Eugene (2019), Kader and Roman (2018) as well as Kemjika and Obikoya (2017) who all reported significant relationship between family conflicts or dysfunction and school adjustment of students.

From research findings two, it is revealed that there is no significant relationship between family values and school adjustment of secondary school adolescent in Bayelsa State. This finding implies irrespective of the values which each family upholds, this may not relate to the extent to which adolescents from such homes can adjust or misadjust in school. In other words, family believes, practices and values are not connected with student ability to adjust while in school. The implication here is that student who come from families with high values may adjust or mal-adjust in school likewise those from homes with low values. This further means that in practice, they may be student or adolescent from well cultured homes but may be involved in lot of maladjusted behaviors like fighting, smoking, bullying etc. The findings of the study somehow is surprising to the researcher because to the best of her knowledge, the family is the primary agent of socialization and training in which the children will adopt greater part of their personality. Therefore, it is surprising to reveal that adjustment or mal-adjustment is unconnected with family values. These current findings differ from Geel and Vedder (2011), Olaitan (2007) Uwaifo (2012) as well as Akanbi et al (2017) who all reported significant relationship between family values and student adjustment in secondary schools.

From research finding three, it is revealed that there is a significant relationship between self-esteem and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State. This finding means that the way adolescents carries themselves may influence the way he or she may be able to adjust while in school. In other words, adolescent with poor self-esteem may find it difficult to fit in with their classmates while interacting and vice versa. Again, those with high self-esteem may also either “fit in” or adjust easily with others or may on the other hand isolate themselves from others as a result of differences in class. The findings of the study is not surprising once again to the researcher because she is aware that the way an individual carries himself determines how they will be able to fit in or adjust to certain things. The finding as reported by Devi (2023), Yadav and Srivastava (2021) as well as Pasha and Munaf (2013) all supported the current findings.

CONCLUSION

The problem of lack of adjustment in schools among adolescents has been a reoccurring threat. From lack of association to bullying and manifestation of unruly behavior, this has been a source of concern to parents, teachers as well as counselors. However, the problem of adjustment or maladjustment are embedded in a lot of factors and the major one among them is, the family type and the nature of family relationship as well as the attachment patterns with the parents. Again, psychological factor like the self-esteem of the adolescent is also major factors that affect the social adjustment of the students. However, proper management by the parents, teachers as well as school counselors can go a long way to minimize the negative effect of this ugly trend.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Parents should be careful with the type of interaction between themselves in the presence of the children since this can cause either positive or negative adjustments in the life of the children. Hence, parents should reduce conflict at home and even when there are issues, they should sort it out amicably.
2. Teachers and counselors should know the family history of the students in order to identify and help those who come from dysfunctional families.
3. Although there is an insignificant relationship between family values and school adjustment of adolescents, it is yet recommended that families should try as much as possible to uphold positive values because the researcher still believes that this can go a long way to help the children to adjust properly in school.

Challenges associated with difficult terrain, instrument mortality as well as respondent bias where few challenges encountered by the researcher in the course of the study.

Contribution to knowledge

The study has empirically established that family variables, psychosocial variables are lead causes of adjustment among students. Hence, it has serve as appropriate references when carrying out similar studies. Also, in the course of the study, some instrument were develop, or modified and used for data collection. These have added new knowledge to would be users.

REFERENCES

- Agbakwuru, C. (2009). *School adjustment*. Joe Mankpa Publishers.
- Agbakwuru, C., & Ekechukwu, R. (2009). *Sexuality education and reproductive health counselling for adolescents*. Owerri, State: Career Publishers.
- Browne, K. (2009). The risk of harm to young children in institutional care. *Better Care Network*. Retrieved 29 November 2013 from http://www.crin.org/docs/the_Risk_of_Harm.pdf
- Darner, R. (2009). Self-Determination theory as a guide to fostering environmental motivation. *Reports & Research*, 40 (2):39-49.
- Demirtas-Zorbaz, S. & Ergene, T. (2019). School adjustment of first-grade primary school students: Effects of family involvement, externalizing behavior, teacher and peer relations. *Children and youth services review*. 101. 307-316. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2019.04.019>.
- Ehibudu, E.I.R., & Obikoya, O.G (2017). Family conflicts and attachment patterns as correlates of school adjustment among public senior secondary school students in Rivers State. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 23(10), 10-21.
- Ekeremo, P. E. (2008). *Understanding who the adolescents is: A wholistic approach*. Enugu. Beauty press.
- Ella, R. E., Odok, A. O., & Ella, G. E. (2015). Influence of Family Size and Family Type on Academic Performance of Students in Government in Calabar Municipality, Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities Social Sciences and Education*, 2 (11), 108-114.
- Geel, M. & Vedder, P. (2011). The role of family obligations and school adjustment in Explaining the Immigrant Paradox. *J Youth Adolesc*. 40(2): 187–196.
- Hahn, D.B. & Payne, W.A (2011). *Focus on health* (5th ed). New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Iruloh, B.N, Ehibudu, I.J and Echebe. P.I. (2009). *Organization and administration of guidance and counselling services; In school And Non-school setting*. Uniport press, choba.
- Kemjika, O. G., & Obikoya, O. G. (2017). Relationship between family conflict, values and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents In Rivers State. retrieved from <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/relationship-between-family-conflict%2c-values-and-of-Kemjika-Obikoya/874421da79a8687a7778e18c3aaafc1f30ec0757>

- Lakhani, P. K, Jain, K, Chandel, P. K. (2017). School adjustment, motivation and academic achievement among students. *International Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 7(10), 333-348. www.researchgate.com.
- Malek, T. (2013). *Emotional intelligence in modifying social and academic adjustment among First Year University Students in North Jordan*. Department of Counseling and Psychology, College of Arts and Science University Utara Malaysia.
- Okpara, I. M. & Onyekuru, B. U. D. (2013). Psychosocial predictors of secondary school students adjustment to school. *European Scientific Journal*. 9(17). <https://doi.org/10.19044/esj.2013.v9n17p%25p>.
- Onwuasoanya, P.N. (2008) (ed.). *Counseling psychology for Nigeria*. Nsukka: Great Express Publishers Ltd.
- Santrock, J. W. (2008). *Adolescence (12th ed)*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Sharma, R., & Saini, N. K. (2014). A critical appraisal of Kuppaswamy's Socio-economic status scale in the present scenario. *Journal of Family and Medical Primary Care*, 3(1): 3–4.
- Shaver, P. R., & Cassidy J. (2018). *Handbook of attachment: Theory, research and clinical applications*. New York and London: Guilford Press. pp. 269–94.
- Smith, E. R., & Mackie, D. M. (2007). *Social psychology*. New York: Psychology Press.
- Smojver-Ažić, S. Dorčić, T. M & Juretić, J (2015). Contribution of parental attachment and involvement to the academic, emotional and social adjustment to college: A three-year longitudinal study. *Horizons of Psychology*, 24, 21–32.
- Yadav, S. & Srivastava, S. K. (2021). A Study of Self Esteem and Adjustment among Students. 9(3):2242 -2246. DOI: [10.25215/0903.215](https://doi.org/10.25215/0903.215).